

Adaptive Conversational Agents through Cognitive and Emotion-Aware User Profiling

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Abstract. Conversational agents powered by large language models (LLMs) have advanced significantly, but they often lack adaptation to users’ emotional and cognitive profiles, limiting adaptive interactions. This article presents an adaptive conversational framework that combines user profiling, including medical, emotion, and cognitive characteristics, with contextual adaptation using retrieval-augmented generation. Using real-world user profiles paired with both original and adapted health-related questions, we build an automated pipeline to dynamically generate responses that adjusts response tone and complexity. A subjective evaluation shows strong alignment between adapted responses and user needs. The proposed framework provides a scalable path toward more inclusive, user-centred conversational systems.

Keywords: Conversational agents · Large language models · User profiling · Context-aware systems · Human-computer interaction

1 Introduction

The proliferation of large language models (LLMs) has significantly advanced the capabilities of conversational agents in human-computer interaction (HCI). While these models are excellent at producing fluent and coherent responses, they often operate without a nuanced understanding of the user’s emotional state, cognitive ability, or specific context. As a result, conversations can feel generic, emotionally mismatched, or cognitively inaccessible to many users, especially in domains such as healthcare or assistive support, where tailored communication is crucial [2, 4].

Recent research has emphasised the importance of multimodal systems and context-aware adaptation. Advances in affective computing and multimodal emotion recognition has shown that integrating signals such as speech tone, physiological responses, and facial gestures can significantly enhance interaction quality

[1, 8]. Similarly, advancements in edge-deployable LLMs have opened pathways for private, responsive AI systems that comply with regulatory demands, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁵ and the AI Act [5]. Efforts like retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) further boost personalisation by combining external knowledge in the form of vectorial datasets with generative models [9]. However, while technical frameworks exist for personalisation and there are domain-specific precedents [6], few studies have operationalised these in structured multi-dimensional experiments that incorporate medical and cognitive profiling alongside adaptive dialogue generation.

To address this gap, we propose a framework that integrates structured user profiles, medical conditions, emotional level (emotional sensitivity), and cognitive capacity into a prompt adaptation layer for LLMs. These profiles guide both the tone and complexity of interactions. Through experiments involving five diverse user profiles (i.e., targeting senior population) and customised queries, we explore how emotional and cognitive diversity can be embedded into HCI.

2 Methodology

The methodology (Fig. 1) behind our adaptive conversational agent framework is as follows. First, a dataset with users’ medical data was processed to generate a medical profile for each user. Second, such user profiles were combined with auxiliary information from the users, including emotional and cognitive capabilities, to create a vectorial dataset (i.e., used for RAG). Next, a set of questions were adapted to be answered based on the user’s data using predefined prompt-based logic. Such a prompt was constructed and sent to a local instance of Llama3.3 (70B of parameters quantised to 4B⁶) using a structured system message. Finally, the query, profile metadata, and generated answer were logged for further evaluation. Such an experimental framework enabled consistent and reproducible testing of the AI agent’s adaptability in providing personalised responses, considering each user’s context.

To obtain the data to generate the medical profile, we used data from the Health and Retirement Study (HRS), a well-known longitudinal study that surveys a representative sample of older adults in the United States. Specifically, we used the HRS Core 2022 dataset and extracted over 70 medical variables of interest from *Section C: Physical Health* to create realistic profiles. Such variables include, among others, self-reported overall health, medical conditions such as diabetes, osteoporosis, cholesterol issues, and joint problems, as well as health-related habits like hours spent sitting, smoking, and alcohol consumption.

We generated five user profiles to test the functionality of our proposal, each characterised by (i) a medical condition extracted from the dataset as detailed previously, (ii) an emotional score ranging from 1 to 5, and (iii) a cognitive level from 1 to 5. These values were used to guide the tone, complexity, and responsiveness of the interaction. Note that the selected levels were designed to provide

⁵ <https://gdpr.eu/>

⁶ <https://ollama.com/library/llama3.3:latest>

Fig. 1. Detail of the pipeline. On the left, the medical data from the users, as well as other auxiliary data, are processed with an LLM to generate a vectorial dataset for RAG. On the right, given an authenticated user, the agent processes the query with the contextual user’s data retrieved from the RAG to provide personalised responses.

Table 1. Interpretation of emotional and cognitive level scales.

Level	Emotion Interpretation	Cognitive Interpretation
1	Very rude or harsh tone; prefers blunt, fast, and highly factual responses; easily annoyed by emotional language.	High cognitive ability; highly literate, comfortable with abstract and technical concepts, and requires minimal simplification.
2	Slightly irritable; prefers direct language but tolerates some nuance; dislikes overly emotional or vague explanations.	Basic understanding of concepts; can follow clear and simple logic but avoids technical terminology.
3	Neutral to moderately sensitive; prefers a calm, respectful tone; appreciates straightforward but kind language.	Moderate comprehension; capable of processing average-level explanations with some simplification.
4	Sensitive or easily discouraged; prefers supportive and affirming tone; avoids confrontation or stress-inducing phrasing.	Low cognitive ability; needs simplified explanations using everyday language and concrete examples.
5	Very emotionally vulnerable or anxious; needs maximum empathy and emotional reassurance in all communication.	Very low cognitive capacity or literacy; requires extremely simple, step-by-step explanations using basic vocabulary and repetition.

a preliminary, comprehensive set of profiles and do not intend to represent all the details, intricacies, and possible variations. Table 1 defines the interpretation of emotional and cognitive values, and Table 2 provides the summary of the medical profile. Note that we generated a set of profiles to ensure that the responses adapted to each of them. Next, for each profile, we generated a set of responses given the following questions: *Q1 - Which are my current main health risks?*, *Q2 - Which medical advice should I follow to have a better life quality?*, *Q3 - What does a healthy daily routine look like in my case?*. Due to space constraints and for the sake of reproducibility, all data including medical data, profiles, and responses adapted to a subset of 5 users has been made public⁷.

As observed, profiles with higher emotional values were provided with emotionally reassuring and slow-paced responses, while those with lower cognitive scores received simpler explanations. In contrast, users with low emotion or high

⁷ <https://smarttechresearch.com/opendata/UCAmI2025-Agents/>

Table 2. Detail of test user profile and medical summary extracted from the dataset, as well as the assigned cognitive and emotional levels. The cognitive level of the user was 1 and the emotional level was 5.

Medical Profile Condition

This individual, presents with a generally good health evaluation but has several notable conditions and risk factors. They have hypertension, for which they are being medicated, and cardiac disease. Additionally, they have high cholesterol, indicating a need for monitoring and possibly management of lipid profiles to mitigate cardiovascular risk. There is no indication of diabetes, cancer (excluding skin), pulmonary disease, stroke, emotional/psychiatric problems, depression, Alzheimer’s, dementia, arthritis, or sleep disorders. Their vision and hearing are good to very good, with no reported problems with sleeping, waking up at night, or waking up too early. They do not have pain problems, incontinence, joint replacement history, or a weakened immune system.

The individual is up to date on certain vaccinations, including influenza and COVID-19 vaccines. However, their physical activity level is concerning, with almost never or never engaging in vigorous activity, only once a week in moderate activity, and more than once a week in light activity. They spend a significant amount of time sitting (5 hours per day).

Their history includes alcohol consumption, with 6 days per week of alcohol use and an average of 2 drinks per day, which may be relevant to their hypertension and cardiac disease management. There is no current smoking, but the history of tobacco use is not provided. Risk factors include hypertension, high cholesterol, cardiac disease, and a sedentary lifestyle, which collectively increase the risk for further cardiovascular events. Management of these conditions through medication adherence, lifestyle modifications (including increased physical activity and potentially dietary changes), and monitoring of cholesterol levels will be crucial in mitigating these risks. Regular follow-up with healthcare providers to assess the effectiveness of current treatments and to adjust them as necessary is recommended.

cognition received more facts, technical, and concise responses. In all cases, the agent produced responses that (i) used emotionally supportive and simple phrasing, and (ii) structured information in short, reassuring statements. Note that the goal of these experiments was not just to demonstrate technological feasibility but to highlight how structured profile-based adaptation using RAG and LLMs could personalise conversational AI systems in medically relevant and emotionally nuanced contexts.

3 Discussion

Upon subjective review performed and peer-reviewed by the authors of the article, the responses generated for the tested user showed strong alignment with the profile’s needs. The medical condition analysed in the response is well interpreted by the agent, considering the extracted data, and is translated clearly to the user in a soft and encouraging explanation, avoiding excessive technical vocabulary while offering clarity. Moreover, the response to concerns about health risks avoided alarming language and instead emphasised support and gradual decline, using language like ‘‘I want to start by acknowledging that it takes a

Table 3. Comparison of adapted and standard responses for the test user.

	Standard Response		
	Q1	Q2	Q3
Q1	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.
Q2	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.
Q3	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.	Based on your medical profile, to improve your specific health conditions, including hypertension, I want to focus on managing your diet, exercise, and stress levels. I've created a personalized plan for you that includes a daily routine of walking, stretching, and meditation. I've also included a list of healthy recipes and a guide to stress management techniques. I hope this helps you feel better and more in control of your health. Let me know if you have any questions or need further assistance.

lot of courage to face your health concerns’’ to reduce anxiety. Finally routine suggestions were phrased in gentle, concrete terms that matched the user’s emotional and cognitive context.

While a robust evaluation framework, based on real users and questionnaires, would be necessary to assess the proposed system, the preliminary outcomes suggest the framework is effective in producing emotionally intelligent and cognitively appropriate content when guided by structured profile data. Therefore, the results demonstrate the system’s capability to accommodate highly sensitive user contexts and provide a proof-of-concept for expanding such personalisation to broader, real-world applications.

Results demonstrate that tailoring conversational agents to user profiles across emotional, cognitive, and medical dimensions, enhances the contextual relevance and personalisation of responses compared to generic LLM outputs. In the tested case, the agent successfully adapted to a user with high emotional sensitivity and cognitive ability, providing clear and supportive responses that maintained informational value without causing overload. Real-world profiles enabled repeatable testing across varied scenarios, supported by a Python backend that generated prompts based on defined profile variables.

Despite promising results, limitations remain. Real-world interactions may introduce unpredictable user behaviours, and the subjective mapping of emotional and cognition requires validation through user studies and questionnaires. Still, the approach highlights the importance of structured contextual profiles in conversational agents, especially in healthcare, education, and assistive technologies. Last but not least, this reinforces the need for responsible AI that accommodates emotional and cognitive diversity [3, 7].

4 Conclusions

We presented an adaptive conversational agent framework that personalises interactions using user profiles based on medical, emotional, and cognitive traits. By combining these profiles with LLMs and RAG, the system dynamically adjusted tone and complexity to fit the user’s needs. Experiments showed improved emotional sensitivity and cognitive accessibility by providing conversations adapted to each user’s profile. The framework was implemented to provide automated, seamless interactions, enabling scalable and structured personalisation. These findings highlight the importance of profile-aware adaptation in conversational AI. Future work will involve the use of smaller LLM models to assess whether these can accurately capture the context and provide high-quality, personalised conversations. In parallel, we will study the creation of indicators extracted from well-known benchmarks to characterise cognitive levels and emotion, aiming to validate the system with real data.

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